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STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF SULODEXIDE ON THE STATE OF ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION IN PATIENTS WITH ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE HISTORY OF MYOCARDIAL REVASCULARISATION

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Abstract

The article presents the results of a study devoted to investigating the effect of sulodexide on endothelial function in patients with ischaemic heart disease who have undergone myocardial revascularisation. Patients with stable angina pectoris, with and without type 2 diabetes mellitus, were examined. Endothelial function was assessed based on cuff test data and levels of endothelin-1, interleukin-6, and VEGF. It was shown that patients with diabetes mellitus had a higher severity of endothelial dysfunction. A 6-month course of sulodexide therapy improved endothelial function and reduced laboratory markers of inflammation. The data confirm the efficacy and safety of sulodexide in the complex therapy of patients with IHD.

Keywords: ischaemic heart disease; endothelial dysfunction; sulodexide; type 2 diabetes mellitus; endothelium-dependent vasodilation; endothelin-1; VEGF; interleukin-6; cuff test; reactive hyperaemia.

Relevance. Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) remain the leading cause of mortality and disability in both economically developed countries and countries with economies in transition. According to an analysis of overall mortality by region in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2021, there were 174,541 deaths, of which 61.5% were due to diseases of the circulatory system [1, 2, 3].

In patients with ischaemic heart disease (IHD) and diabetes mellitus (DM), the ability of endothelial cells to synthesise nitric oxide (NO) and release vasorelaxing factors is reduced, while the production of vasoconstrictive substances is maintained or even increased. This results in an imbalance between the mediators that ensure normal endothelial function, which manifests itself in the development of endothelial dysfunction (ED) [4].

The main manifestations of ED include impaired endothelium-dependent vasodilation and increased adhesive properties of the vascular lining. Coronary artery endothelial dysfunction is accompanied by a decrease in coronary reserve and the inability of blood vessels to dilate adequately when myocardial oxygen demand increases, which contributes to the onset and progression of ischaemia [5, 6]. Endothelial dysfunction is characteristic of patients at risk of developing coronary atherosclerosis, and in patients already diagnosed with IHD, it becomes an important marker of cardiovascular events (CVEs).

In recent years, there has been growing interest in the study and treatment of ED. There are many methods for diagnosing it, but the cuff test is considered the most non-invasive. Tatsuya Maruhashi et al. investigated the effectiveness of this method in Japanese individuals

[7], while Ernesto Dallia et al. used it to assess the severity of ED in patients with risk factors for coronary artery disease and acute myocardial infarction [8]. In their study, the worst cuff test results were observed in patients with acute myocardial infarction.

In addition to instrumental methods, laboratory markers play a significant role in the assessment of ED. Among them, endothelin-1 (ET-1), vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) and interleukin-6 (IL-6) are of particular importance, as their levels reflect the severity of endothelial dysfunction.

Given the high prevalence of ED, particular attention is paid to the search for pharmacological agents capable of improving endothelial function. Salma Charfeddine et al. demonstrated the positive effect of sulodexide in patients with IHD against the background of COVID-19: the drug contributed to a significant improvement in endothelial function, a reduction in the frequency of angina attacks and a decrease in tachycardia [9].

In this regard, our study aims to investigate the effect of sulodexide on endothelial function in patients with IHD, both with and without diabetes mellitus.

Research objective. To investigate the effect of sulodexide on arterial endothelial function in patients with IHD, depending on the presence of type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Materials and methods. The study included 70 patients with ischaemic heart disease (IHD) and stable exertional angina of functional class (FC) I–IV, who had a history of surgical or endovascular myocardial revascularisation — coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG) or percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) — more than one year ago.

As a control group (CG), 20 practically healthy individuals with no clinical signs of cardiovascular pathology were examined.

All patients in the main group were divided into two subgroups depending on the presence of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM):

- Group 1 — 36 patients without T2DM;
- Group 2 — 34 patients diagnosed with T2DM.

All patients examined had stage III arterial hypertension (AH) and chronic heart failure (CHF) of functional class I–III according to the New York Heart Association (NYHA) classification.

Exclusion criteria included patients:

- with a high risk of bleeding;
- who had undergone myocardial revascularisation less than 1 year prior to inclusion;
- receiving dual or triple antiplatelet therapy;
- with gastric or duodenal ulcer;
- with a history of acute cerebrovascular accident;
- with atrial fibrillation requiring oral anticoagulants;
- with a history of haemorrhoidal bleeding episodes.

All patients received standard drug therapy, including acetylsalicylic acid (75 mg/day), statins, β -blockers, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors or sartans, and mineralocorticoid receptor antagonists.

When comparing baseline clinical and laboratory parameters, both groups were comparable in terms of age, blood pressure, and body mass index (BMI) (Table 1). Significant differences were found in fasting blood glucose, glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) and creatinine levels (Table 1). The clinical and laboratory characteristics of the patients examined are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Clinical and laboratory characteristics of the patients examined.

Index	1 group (non DM)	2 group (with DM)	Control group
Age, years	65,49±1,05	65,86±1,24	42,37±2,64**
BMI, kg/m ²	29,79±0,86	29,89±0,49	22,35±0,32*
SBP, mmHg	138,16±25,35	138,27±6,26	118,41±5,22*
DBP, mmHg	77,74±9,73	78,33±3,06	70,26±4,18*
HbA1, %	5,19±0,14	7,53±0,28^^	5,23±0,12*
Glicemia, mmol/l	5,22±0,12	8,79±0,53^^	5,02±0,15*
EF, %	53,18±6,20	51,56±6,87	64,85 ± 4,91*
CABG in anamnes, n	7 (19,4%)	9 (26,5%)	-
TCI in anamnesis, n	29 (80,6%)	25 (73,6%)	-

Note: difference between the main group and GC: * - $p < 0.05$, ** - $p < 0.01$; difference between main groups I and II: ^- $p < 0.05$, ^^ - $p < 0.01$

All examined patients underwent a comprehensive clinical and instrumental examination, including assessment of anthropometric parameters (body weight, kg; height, cm; body mass index — BMI, kg/m²), blood

pressure (BP) measurement, and laboratory tests (fasting blood glucose, mmol/l; lipid spectrum indicators, mmol/l).

The state of vascular endothelial function (EF) was assessed based on a combination of laboratory and

instrumental data. In particular, the levels of endothelin-1 (ET-1), interleukin-6 (IL-6) and vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) in blood serum were determined, and Doppler ultrasound of the brachial artery (BA) was performed.

For instrumental assessment of EF, a reactive hyperemia test (cuff test) was used according to the method of D. Celermajer et al. (1992). The diameter of the right brachial artery (RBA) was measured using a Philips Affinity 50G ultrasound machine (USA) with a 7 MHz linear probe in B-mode according to generally accepted standards. The artery was visualised in a longitudinal section 2–15 cm above the elbow bend, with the image synchronised with the R wave of the electrocardiogram (ECG). The study was conducted in triplex mode.

At baseline, the diameter of the artery and maximum blood flow velocity were recorded. Doppler ultrasound was performed in the morning, on an empty stomach, with the patient lying on their back, after a 10-minute rest.

To induce reactive hyperemia, a sphygmomanometer cuff was applied to the shoulder, inflating it to a pressure 50 mm Hg above systolic pressure. The cuff was held for 5 minutes, after which the air was quickly released. In the first 15 seconds after decompression, blood flow velocity (BFV) was measured, and during the following 60 seconds, changes in artery diameter were recorded.

The following indicators of brachial artery endothelial function were assessed:

- D_0 (cm) — artery diameter at rest;
- D_1 (cm) — artery diameter after reactive hyperemia (RH) test;
- V_{max} (cm/s) — peak systolic blood flow velocity;
- V_{min} (cm/s) — maximum diastolic velocity;
- IR (u.e.) — resistance index.

Endothelium-dependent vasodilation (EDVD) was calculated using the formula:

$$EDVD = (D_1 - D_0) / D_0 \times 100\%.$$

An increase in brachial artery diameter of more than 10% was considered preserved EVD, while an increase of less than 10% indicated impaired endothelial vasomotor function.

Endothelin-1, VEGF, and IL-6 levels were determined by quantitative enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. VEGF concentration was determined in serum obtained from peripheral venous blood. Blood was collected in the morning on an empty stomach in the supine position after 10 minutes of rest, from the cubital vein, using a vacuum tube. Excessive physical activity was excluded the day before. The blood was centrifuged to obtain serum. VEGF and IL-6 concentrations were measured by solid-phase enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay using the VEGF-IFA-BEST reagent kit manufactured by Vector-Best CJSC (Russia). The concentration of ET-1 was measured by solid-phase enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay using a set of reagents from Elabscience (USA).

After initial examinations, all patients were prescribed sulodexide (Vessel Due F, Catalent Italy, S.P.A. (Italy)) in oral form at a dose of 500 LE/day, divided into 2 doses for a period of 6 months. Six months after treatment with sulodexide, repeat laboratory and instrumental examinations were performed. In order to monitor the safety of sulodexide use, all patients underwent coagulogram assessment and platelet aggregation analysis after 1 and 3 months of treatment with the drug. No cases of haemorrhagic complications were recorded during the study.

Results.

When analysing the functional state of the vascular endothelium in the examined patients, the indicators of endothelium-dependent vasodilation (EDVD) of the brachial artery (BA) deserve special attention (Table 2).

The initial diameter of the BA in patients of both groups did not differ statistically significantly and was 0.45 ± 0.01 cm in patients of group 1 and 0.44 ± 0.01 cm in patients of group 2.

In patients in group 1 (without diabetes mellitus), the PA EVSD index was $7.76 \pm 1.7\%$. In 44.4% ($n=16$) of patients in this group, the vasomotor function of the endothelium was preserved ($EVSD > 10\%$). Endothelial dysfunction (ED) was diagnosed in 20 (55.6%) patients, of whom:

- 10 (27.8%) had insufficient PA diameter increase ($EZVD < 10\%$),
- 7 (19.4%) had no diameter increase,
- 3 (8.4%) developed pathological vasoconstriction.

In the second group, which included patients with diabetes mellitus (DM), vasomotor ED induced by shear stress was detected in all cases. The average EED index in this category of patients was $4.8 \pm 1.29\%$. At the same time:

- 17.6% ($n=6$) of patients had an increase in PA diameter $> 10\%$;
- 44.2% ($n=15$) had impaired vasomotor endothelial function in the form of an insufficient vasodilatory response ($< 10\%$);
- 23.5% ($n=8$) had no increase in diameter;
- 14.7% ($n=5$) had pathological vasoconstriction.

Doppler examination of linear blood flow velocity parameters (V_{max} and V_{min}) revealed no significant differences between the groups. However, the degree of increase in velocity characteristics after the reactive hyperemia test was significantly higher in patients in group 1, indicating a decrease in vasodilator reserve in patients in group 2.

In the control group, the PA ESVD index was $20.2 \pm 1.23\%$ ($p < 0.01$). After removing the compression during the cuff test, a significant increase in blood flow velocity parameters (V_{max} , V_{min}) was noted compared to patients in group 2 ($p < 0.01$). Patients in group 1 also showed a significant increase in velocity parameters, but the severity of the changes was less than in the control group (Table 2).

Table 2.

Baseline indicators of the reactive hyperemia test in the main group (with SD), the comparison group (without SD), and the control group (practically healthy individuals)

Index	CHD non DM		CHD with DM		Control group	
	Before	After	Before	After	Before	After
Diameter a. brachialis, sm	0,45±0,01	0,49±0,01*	0,44±0,01	0,46±0,01	0,44±0,01	0,53±0,01
Vmax, sm/sec	66,1±3,14	77,3±3,87*	71,9±1,69	74,6±2,38	74±1,66	95±1,85**
V min, sm/sec	7,41±0,25	9,14±0,38*	8,58±0,51	8,8±0,62	7,5±0,19	10,1±0,33*
RI, y.e.	0,77±0,01	0,75±0,011	0,8±0,015	0,77±0,013	0,65±0,012	0,6±0,013
Endothelium-dependent vasodilation, %	7,76±1,7°		4,8±1,29		20,2±1,23^^^	

Note: significance of differences between initial and post-trial indicators: *- p<0.05, ** - p<0.01; the difference between the indicators in the main group and the control group is significant ^^ - p<0.001; the difference between the initial indicators of the main groups I and II: ° - p<0.05

When studying baseline laboratory indicators assessing endothelial function in patients with and without diabetes, a significant increase in IL-6, ET-1, and VEGF indicators was noted compared to the control group (p<0.001) (Table 3). When comparing laboratory parameters in patients from the two main groups, a more significant increase in ED parameters was noted in patients with DM. For example, IL-6 in patients in group I was 36.49±3.78 pg/ml, while in patients in group II it was 59.76±4.91 (p<0.01). ET-1 was also higher in patients with SD (230.47±59.55 pg/ml vs. 184.9±49.1 pg/ml, respectively, p<0.05). VEGF in the group without DM was 687.26±64.2 pg/ml, whereas in patients with DM this indicator was 998.24±77.55 pg/ml (p<0.001).

Next, an analysis of endothelial function in patients after a 6-month course of treatment with sulodexide was performed. As can be seen from Table 4, after

a course of treatment with sulodexide, a significant improvement in cuff test indicators was noted in patients in both groups (p<0.05), but in patients without diabetes, the improvement in EF was more pronounced than in those with diabetes. In patients in group I, D1 increased from 0.49±0.01 cm to 0.54±0.02 cm (p<0.05), Vmin at 1 minute from 9.14±0.38 cm/s to 11.7±0.41 cm/s (p<0.05), EZVD increased from 7.76±1.7% to 10.48±2.15% (p<0.05), IR decreased from 0.77±0.01 to 0.7±0.013 (p<0.05), IR at 1 minute also decreased from 0.75±0.011 to 0.68±0.012 (p<0.05) (Table 4). All this indicates better vascular endothelial function and the ability of blood vessels to adequately vasodilate. In patients in group II, ESVD increased from 4.8 ± 1.29% to 6.95 ± 1.3% (p < 0.05), IR decreased from 0.8 ± 0.015 to 0.73 ± 0.014 (p < 0.05), IR at 1 minute also decreased from 0.77±0.013 to 0.70±0.013 (p<0.05) (Table 4). Thus, the indicators reflecting the improvement in EF during the cuff test are a decrease in IR, IR at 1 minute, and an increase in EDVD.

Table 4.

Dynamics of cuff test indicators in examined patients after 6 months of treatment with sulodexide

Index	CHD nonDM		CHD with DM	
	Before	After	Before	After
D0, sm	0,45±0,01	0,45±0,01	0,44±0,01	0,45±0,01
D1, sm	0,49±0,01	0,54±0,02*	0,46±0,01	0,5±0,01
Vmax, sm/sec	66,1±3,14	69,5±3,5	71,9±1,69	70,6±3,8
Vmin, sm/sec	7,41±0,25	7,7 ±0,27	8,58±0,51	8,3±0,47
RI, y.e.	0,77±0,01	0,7 ±0,013*	0,8±0,015	0,73±0,014*
Vmax 1 min, sm/sec	77,3±3,87	85,6±4,32	74,6±2,38	78,7±3,68
Vmin 1 min, sm/sec	9,14±0,38	11,7±0,41*	8,8±0,62	9,6±0,53
RI 1 min, y.e.	0,75±0,011	0,68±0,012*	0,77±0,013	0,70±0,013*
EDVD, %	7,76±1,7	10,48±2,15*	4,8±1,29	6,95±1,3*

Note: difference in indicators before and after treatment in patients in the same group: *- p<0.05

In addition to the cuff test, patients also underwent repeated laboratory blood tests for IL-6, ET-1, and VEGF concentrations. After a 6-month course of treatment with sulodexide, a significant improvement in IL-6 and ET-1 indicators was observed in patients in both groups, but VEGF decreased significantly only in patients with diabetes mellitus (Table 5). In patients in group I, IL-6 decreased from 36.49±3.78 pg/ml to 25.34±2.84 pg/ml (p<0.05), ET-1 decreased from

184.9±49.1 pg/ml to 48.69±4.05 pg/ml (p<0.001) (Table 5). In patients in group II, IL-6 decreased from 59.76±4.91 pg/ml to 33.84±3.08 pg/ml (p<0.05), ET-1 decreased from 230.47±59.55 pg/ml to 88.30±22.68 pg/ml (p<0.001), VEGF decreased from 998.24±77.55 pg/ml to 683.33±39.15 pg/ml (p<0.001)

Discussion of the results obtained.

The vascular endothelium plays a key role in maintaining vascular homeostasis [10]. The independent role of the vascular endothelium in regulating vascular tone was first reported in an article by R. Furchgott and J. Zawadzki in 1980. The main role in this was attributed to endothelial cells, which were characterised by the authors as «a cardiovascular endocrine organ that mediates communication between blood and tissues in critical situations» [11]. Subsequently, it was proven that the endothelium is an active organ, the dysfunction of which is mandatory in the pathogenesis of virtually all cardiovascular diseases, including atherosclerosis, hypertension, IHD, CHF, etc.

It has been established that the endothelium indirectly affects vascular tone through the release of vasodilatory and vasoconstrictive factors and modulates the contractile activity of smooth muscle cells [12]. Since endothelial dysfunction contributes to the development and progression of atherosclerosis, which ultimately leads to cardiovascular disease (CVD) [13], researchers are studying strategies for assessing endothelial dysfunction as an early biomarker of cardiovascular disease [14]. In 1992, Celermajer et al. [15] introduced the cuff test for non-invasive assessment of endothelial function using ultrasound. Currently, the cuff test has become a popular diagnostic method for ED due to its non-invasiveness, sensitivity [16], and correlation with coronary artery endothelial function [17].

Meta-analyses show that a 1% increase in ABI is associated with a 12-13% reduction in the likelihood of cardiovascular events, indicating that the cuff test may be a useful vascular biomarker for cardiovascular risk stratification [18]. Clinical studies have demonstrated a relatively close correlation between brachial artery endothelial function, as assessed by cuff testing, and coronary artery endothelial function, assessed by changes in epicardial coronary artery diameter in response to shear stress or intracoronary administration of acetylcholine for 5 minutes [19].

That is why we chose the cuff test as an examination to assess the condition of the endothelium. By applying this research method to patients, we proved a close correlation between this research method and laboratory indicators (IL-6, ET-1, VEGF) reflecting the condition of the endothelium. These laboratory parameters are recognised as markers for assessing the condition of the endothelium [20, 21]. In our study, patients with IHD showed a significant decrease in PVR compared to the control group, but the greatest decrease in PVR was observed in patients with diabetes mellitus. Impaired coronary artery endothelial function, manifested by the inability of blood vessels to dilate adequately when the myocardium's oxygen demand increases, contributes to the onset and progression of ischaemia. In patients with T2DM, it is necessary to assess the vasomotor function of the arterial endothelium to predict cardiovascular complications and diagnose ED at an early stage, which in turn will allow adequate therapy to be initiated and thus improve the quality of life of patients with IHD.

Recently, there has been increasing interest in studying the effect of drugs on the condition of the vascular endothelium. We chose sulodexide as a drug that has a positive effect on the endothelium. There are many studies on the use of sulodexide in patients with coronary artery disease [9]. A group of Turkish scientists has found that sulodexide exerts concentration-dependent inhibition of vasoconstriction, emphasising the critical role of intact endothelium and NO-mediated pathways in this process [22]. This highlights the role of sulodexide in the treatment of pathologies associated with endothelial dysfunction.

However, there are no specific data in the literature on such long-term use of sulodexide in patients with IHD, and there are also few studies comparing the effects of sulodexide on patients depending on the presence of diabetes mellitus. Therefore, our goal was to study this issue. As a result of our study, we examined the efficacy and, most importantly, the safety of long-term sulodexide use in patients with IHD. The results of our study proved the positive effect of sulodexide on the functional state of the endothelium in the form of improved cuff test indicators and reduced laboratory indicators reflecting the severity of ED.

Conclusions. Having analysed all of the above, we can confidently recommend sulodexide at a dose of 500 LE/day for a period of 6 months to patients with IHD, both with and without diabetes mellitus, to improve the functional state of the endothelium. Sulodexide has proven its positive effect on the condition of the endothelium in patients with IHD according to laboratory and instrumental studies. An examination such as a cuff test can be easily used to assess the condition of the endothelium and monitor the effectiveness of treatment, as this diagnostic method is affordable, minimally invasive and informative.

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